

Item amendments

Existing items as given in the [Explanation & Elaboration of the TRIPOD-AI guidelines](#) are presented in normal text. To show how our recommendations may be made concrete in the reporting checklist, we list several amendments to these items *in purple italics* as a starting point for further discussion.

INTRODUCTION - Background

3b Describe the target population and the intended purpose of the prediction model in the context of the care pathway, including its intended users (e.g., healthcare professionals, patients, public)

- Describe who is the target population for the developed or evaluated model, e.g., people of a certain age, in a specific country, or with a specific disease
- Describe the intended purpose of the model, including the clinical decision or guidance the model is intended used to support (*i.e. the targeted treatments, for example* referral for further testing or hospital admission, triage, starting a treatment, or changing a lifestyle) and the point in the care pathway the model is to be intended used
- *Identify for which types of patients the targeted treatment(s) might change compared to current practice when the prediction model is used in practice, and specify in what ways it might change*
- *Specify which treatments are assumed when giving the predictions: i.e. is the prediction assuming treatments would be given as in current care? As if patients would not receive the treatment? As if they would be given some treatment selected by the user when interacting with the prediction model?*
- Describe who the intended users of the model are, and if the model is for healthcare professionals, patients, public or other

METHODS - Participants

6b Describe the eligibility criteria for study participants

- The eligibility criteria for participants should be reported to understand the potential applicability and generalisability of the prediction model
- This includes reporting any restrictions of continuous variables, e.g., age range used to define the eligibility of the included participants
- *Specify if any of the targeted treatments were used as eligibility criteria.*

6c Give details of any treatments received, and how they were handled during model development or evaluation, if relevant

- Any treatments received before or at the start of follow-up should be reported, and

whether and how this was handled during the development or evaluation of the prediction model (if relevant)

- Any treatments received between the moment the prediction model is used and the measurement of the outcome, that could modify the probability of the outcome, should be reported (if relevant)
- *For the targeted treatments, specify how the clinical decisions were made in the development data: for example, were they randomized? Made by clinical experts? Made by the patients?*

METHODS - Predictors

9 *(new sub item)*

- *Explain whether the factors that influenced the targeted treatments are included in the analysis, and if yes, in what way.*

METHODS - Analytical methods

Analysis

12 *(new sub item)*

- *Describe how the targeted treatments are handled in the analysis. E.g., are they included as covariates?*